

SHARED LEADERSHIP AND INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP AS CORRELATES TO TEACHERS WORK PERFORMANCE AND SATISFACTION

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ABSTRACT

Shared leadership refers to a team property whereby leadership is distrusted among team members rather than focused on a single designated leader. This study attempted to determine the impact of shared leadership and interpersonal relationship as correlates to teachers work performance and satisfaction of public school teachers in Tiaong District II. This study is a descriptive -correlational kind of research in which it uses a survey questionnaire. There were 120 teacher-respondents teaching in thirteen schools in Tiaong District II, Division of Quezon, conducted last April 2021. Based on the result, the personal characteristics of the respondents include age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching, indicated that majority were above 35 years old and females. Most of them were married, having bachelor's degree with units in masterals . and rendered 11-16 years in service. The conducted regression revealed that interpersonal has significant predictive power to the shared leadership of the administrator and teachers when it comes to planning, supporting, controlling and evaluation. Specifically, the study uncovered that the indicators mentioned in each variables have an important positive relationship with shared leadership. The results emphasize the need for focus on developing more teachers' interpersonal relationship stimulating shared leadership in teacher communities. The theoretical and practical implications of shared leadership, interpersonal relationships, work performance and satisfaction of teachers were discussed in this paper.

Keywords: shared leadership, interpersonal relationship